

On the Effect of Dilution on the Coagulation of Arsenious Sulphide Hydrosols in its Relation to the Arsenious Oxide Content.

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Recent measurements (Mukherjee and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 627, 733)* of the cataphoretic speeds of particles of colloidal arsenious sulphide under different conditions show (a) that the speed decreases on dilution as also on the addition of arsenious oxide* and (b) that these two factors show some similarities regarding the manner in which the speeds change when different concentrations of potassium chloride are added to the sol, but (c) there is no parallelism between the initial cataphoretic speeds (when no electrolyte has been added) and those at precipitating concentrations of the electrolyte.

Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 349, reference to earlier papers are given therein) has classified colloids as normal and abnormal depending upon their behaviour on dilution. He assumes that the precipitation takes place at the isoelectric point and emphasises that "normally" a colloid requires on dilution a smaller precipitating concentration of an electrolyte. Where the reverse happens, he considers that the relative adsorption of similarly charged ions increases and is responsible for the higher precipitating concentration. In the case of arsenious sulphide, Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1925, 36, 129) has also discussed the effect of dilution in terms of the variation of the contents of arsenious oxide and hydrogen sulphide. In view of the above observations regarding the cataphoretic speeds the behaviour on dilution of this sol containing different amounts of arsenious oxide, has been studied.

Results and Discussion.

The method of determining the coagulating concentrations was as given in earlier papers from this laboratory. 5 C.c. of the sol

* Also results obtained by S. N. Mukherjee shortly to be published.

were always mixed with an equal volume of the electrolyte. Sol A was prepared with a restricted amount of hydrogen sulphide. A saturated solution of arsenious oxide was diluted with twice its volume of water. Equal volumes of the resulting solution and of a solution of hydrogen sulphide were mixed such that part of the oxide was left unconverted into the sulphide. It contained 0.0105 g.-moles of the sulphide and 0.0315 of the oxide per litre. Sols B and C which were mixed with just enough hydrogen sulphide and were free from the oxide had 0.042 and 0.039 gram-moles of the sulphide respectively. A brisk stream of hydrogen was passed to ensure that there were no excess of the sulphide or oxide. The dilutions are given as the ratio of the volume of the stock sol to the volume of water added to it before mixing with the electrolyte. The results with sols A and B are given below.

TABLE I.

Dilution.	BaCl ₂		HCl		KCl		LiCl	
	Sol A	Sol B	Sol A	Sol B	Sol A	Sol B	Sol A	Sol B
1 : 0	0.0014	0.00135	0.037	0.052	0.055	0.071	0.064	0.084
1 : 1	0.0017	0.00145	0.042	0.058	0.070	0.082	0.081	0.101
2 : 3	0.0020	0.0015	0.045	0.061	0.074	—	0.092	0.106
1 : 4	0.0022	0.0018	—	0.068	0.075	0.102	—	0.132

Usher (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 21, 406) advocates the comparison of the coagulating concentrations of the different dilutions which would produce the same effect in intervals proportional to dilution. As the rate of coalescence depends upon the number of particles in unit volume (*i.e.*, on the dilution) the same stage of coalescence will be reached at different times and therefore the above procedure was perhaps intended to show separately the influence of factors other than the decrease in the number of particles per unit volume. It would appear (Smoluchowski, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 129) that this procedure does not wholly obviate the difficulty as the different stages of coalescence are not strictly comparable. The results with sol C following this procedure are however given in the following table.

TABLE II.

Dilution : Sol C	BaCl ₂		KCl		KCl		LiCl	
	Conc. in N.	Time in min.	Conc. in N.	Time in min.	Conc. in N.	Time in min.	Conc. in N.	Time in min.
1 : 0	0·00125	3	0·048	3	0·059	3	0·066	3
1 : 2	0·00125	6	0·046	6	0·066	6	0·080	6
2 : 3	0·00123	9-10	0·048	9-10	0·070	9-10	0·080	9-10

In the above tables one notices a uniform stabilisation on dilution for all the electrolytes excepting barium chloride in Table II. The observations with barium chloride are contrary to the experience of previous workers but agree with those of Mukherjee and Sen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 118, 461). Usher's procedure also shows a stabilising effect of dilution excepting the first column (Table II).

Two sols having the same sulphide content but prepared as below were next compared. Sol E was prepared by dilution from sol D which had a higher sulphide content namely, 0·036 gram-moles per litre. Sol F was prepared in the usual way.

TABLE III.

Sol	HCl	KCl	LiCl	BaCl ₂
D	0·043	0·059	0·069	0·0013
D/3	0·048	0·069	0·085	—
E	0·045	0·062	0·074	0·00135
E/2	0·053	0·074	0·096	—
F	0·046	0·063	0·074	0·00135
F/2	0·050	0·075	0·093	—

Here also dilution results in stabilisation. The coagulating concentrations for sols E and F are very nearly the same. It appears therefore that with a constant procedure for preparation the behaviour depends to a large extent on the sulphide content.

The influence of arsenious oxide has been studied from two different standpoints. In one series, G, different percentages of arsenious oxide were left unconverted by regulating the quantity of saturated hydrogen sulphide but the total arsenic content was kept the same. In the second series, H, quantities of saturated solution

of arsenious oxide and water were added from outside to a stock sol so as to bring their total arsenic content and the relative amounts of arsenious oxide and arsenious sulphide to exactly the same values as those of the corresponding sol G.

Series G/2 and H/2 were prepared by diluting the corresponding sols with an equal volume of water. The number of atoms of arsenic in the form of the free oxide has been given in round figures as percentages of the total number of atoms of arsenic in a definite volume. The total arsenic content in series G and H were 0.042 gram-atoms of arsenic per litre.

TABLE IV.

Series G and G/2.

Percent. of Oxide Sulphide	BaCl ₂		HCl		KCl		LiCl		
	G	G/2	G	G/2	G	G/2	G	G/2	
0	100	0.00135	0.0014	0.056	0.063	0.068	0.079	0.080	0.094
5	95	0.00135	0.0014	0.084	0.087	0.048	0.051	0.048	0.060
15	85	0.00135	0.0015	0.082	0.086	0.041	0.051	0.050	0.052
35	65	0.00198	0.0015	0.081	0.086	0.048	0.053	0.050	0.062
55	45	0.00135	0.0016	0.082	0.086	0.044	0.056	0.052	0.060
80	20	0.00145	0.0018	0.084	0.087	0.048	0.065	0.058	0.072

TABLE V.

Series H and H/2

Percent. of Oxide Sulphide	BaCl ₂		HCl		KCl		LiCl		
	H	H-2	H	H-2	H	H-2	H	H-2	
0	100	0.00135	0.0014	0.056	0.063	0.068	0.079	0.080	0.094
5	95	0.00135	0.00146	0.086	0.041	0.048	0.058	0.057	0.069
15	85	0.00180	0.00150	0.086	0.042	0.050	0.050	0.057	0.073
35	65	0.00135	0.00155	0.087	0.044	0.051	0.063	0.062	0.076
45	55	0.00140	0.00160	0.087	0.044	0.053	0.068	0.062	0.076

Series G and H show on the whole a similar behaviour. There is a marked lowering of the coagulating concentration so far as the univalent cations are concerned when the percentage of sulphide

changes from 100 to 95. On further decrease of the sulphide content the coagulating concentrations change only slightly but at the lowest percentages of the sulphide they show a perceptible increase. Thus the sensitisation is followed by stabilisation. The coagulating concentrations of barium chloride show a similar behaviour with the difference that sensitisation is not observed. Further the observed stabilisation with univalent cations is not so marked as the sensitisation but with barium chloride the stabilisation is quite marked. Comparing the corresponding members of G and G/2 or H and H/2 series it will be observed that dilution invariably results in stabilisation but the percentage change in the coagulating concentration fairly remains constant, independent of the ratio of sulphide to oxide. The coagulating concentration of barium chloride increases with dilution in all these cases. It would seem that these sols in which there was little or no free hydrogen sulphide in excess (and in most cases there was an actual excess of free arsenious oxide) show a characteristic behaviour in this respect.

The first horizontal rows in Tables IV and V give the coagulating concentrations of the same sol. A comparison of the corresponding members of series G and H will show that the coagulating concentrations for series H are in general higher than that for series G with the exception of barium chloride which gives practically the same concentration for both series and in some cases gives a smaller concentration for series H. The two series are not identical and even with these slight differences in the method of preparation the properties of the sol are not determined by the sulphide and oxide content.

The stabilisation with decreasing sulphide content and increasing oxide content observed with barium chloride, requires more detailed discussion. It has been taken for granted by previous workers (Dhar, *loc. cit.* ; see however, Mukherjee and Sen, *loc. cit.*) that dilution of this colloid has always a sensitising action against coagulation by barium chloride. In the case of monovalent cations dilution has always been observed, on the contrary, to produce a stabilising action. Reference has been made before to the fact that on increasing the amounts of arsenious oxide while keeping the sulphide content constant, it is observed that the coagulating concentrations of both potassium and barium chloride diminish. It has also been stated that the cataphoretic speed shows a regular decrease under the same conditions. The observed sensitising action of an increased oxide

content has been pointed out by Dhar. We thus see that in the case of the univalent cations, the decreasing sulphide content and the increasing oxide content in both the series (G and H) should produce respectively a stabilising and a sensitising action. This is in perfect agreement with the observed variation in the coagulating concentration which points to the action of two opposite effects as contemplated above. The results with barium chloride however go against the point of view of Dhar as both the decreasing sulphide content and the increasing oxide content should have a sensitising effect. Dhar and co-workers ignore the stabilising action of dilution resulting from an increase in the distance between the particles (or, in other words, the smaller number of particles per unit volume) pointed out by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) and Kruyt (*Kolloid Z.*, 1919, 25, 1). It would appear however that the considerations advanced by Dhar do not account for the uniformly higher coagulating concentration of barium chloride, whereas the stabilising action of the increase in the distance does. Mukherjee and Sen (*loc. cit.*) pointed out that the behaviour on dilution is the result of two opposing effects namely, stabilisation consequent on an increase in the distance between the particles and sensitisation resulting from a diminution of the colloid—liquid interface. They also pointed out, in the absence of relevant data, that they are assuming that the particles do not change in any way as a result of the dilution. It has since been observed that the cataphoretic speed of particles of this sol decreases on dilution. Thus a smaller cataphoretic speed does not necessarily mean a sensitisation as observed with an increased oxide content. This contrast points again to the stabilising effect that dilution as such has. If this be recognised the uniformly higher coagulating concentration of barium chloride finds a sufficient explanation.

Dhar assumes that in view of the higher coagulating concentration of potassium chloride, chlorine ions are adsorbed to a greater extent on dilution. This has the effect of increasing the charge and of stabilising the sol. He also points out that as the coagulating concentration of the barium chloride is low there is no such stabilising action. There is only the sensitising action of a diminution in the interface consequent upon dilution (which was first pointed out by Freundlich) to be considered. The coagulating concentrations of potassium and barium chloride given in this paper are of about the same strength as observed by Dhar. This explanation therefore fails. It may be pointed out that dilution of the colloid in the

experiments of Dhar is least expected to increase the equilibrium concentration of the chlorine ions in the case of potassium chloride as the amount is assumed to be negligible in comparison to the total quantity of ions present. Of course, the nature of the interface may change. Further, a consideration of the fact that the sols used in this work have a different composition and that a diminution in the oxide content is responsible for the observed stabilisation also fails to account for the stabilisation against barium chloride observed in series G and H.

The effect of saturating with hydrogen sulphide a sol containing neither arsenious oxide nor hydrogen sulphide in excess and then driving the free hydrogen sulphide out by hydrogen was next studied. Two sols were prepared, one by the addition of hydrogen sulphide solution to a solution of arsenious oxide such that all the oxide was just converted into the sulphide without it being necessary to pass a stream of hydrogen sulphide gas through it. A portion of this sol, J, was tested and found to be free from excess of arsenious oxide or hydrogen sulphide. It was kept as usual in a Jena glass bottle with a black wrapper. Through a second portion a stream of hydrogen sulphide gas was passed for ten minutes after which the excess was removed by a stream of hydrogen (sol K). The coagulating concentrations were all determined in the same day.

TABLE VI.

HCl		KCl		LiCl		BaCl ₂	
Sol J.	J/2.	J.	J/2.	J.	J/2.	J.	J/2.
0.037	0.042	0.053	0.066	0.061	0.08	0.0013	0.0015
Sol K.	K/2.	K.	K/2.	K.	K/2.	K.	K/2.
0.046	0.050	0.0069	0.075	0.074	0.093	0.00135	0.00155

Sol K shows greater stability than sol J including the case of barium chloride. The higher concentration of barium chloride is curious in view of the opposite observation of Mukherjee and Sen (*loc. cit.*, confirmed by Dhar and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*, *Kolloid Z.*) on half saturation with hydrogen sulphide. The amount of adsorbed and free hydrogen sulphide, which determines the nature and number of ions in the interfacial double layer, is probably different in the two cases and is responsible for this difference.

In view of the uniform stabilisation on dilution against coagulation by barium chloride observed in this paper, measurements of cataphoretic speeds (for procedure see Mukherjee and co-workers, *loc. cit.*) were made with one sol L prepared so as to contain neither excess of hydrogen sulphide nor of arsenious oxide. The results are given below. The speeds have been corrected for alterations in viscosity taking that for water as unity.

TABLE VII.

Sol L.

Conc. of potassium chloride	...	0	0.002	0.004	0.01	0.025	0.045
Cataphoretic speeds	...	67.6	50.5	54.7	53(P)	58.8	56.1
Conc. of barium chloride	...	0	0.0002	0.005	0.0067	—	0.0099*
Cataphoretic speeds	...	67.6	34.9	23.5	22	—	19.1

The speeds show variations similar to that observed before and on that ground it is difficult to account for the different behaviour against coagulation by barium chloride.

Summary.

(a) It has been observed that increasing concentrations of arsenious oxide sensitise the sol in keeping with the observed decrease in cataphoretic speeds.

(b) On the other hand, dilution diminishes the speed but stabilises the sol. This contrast cannot be accounted for on the basis of a change in the concentration of arsenious oxide but can best be accounted for by a consideration of the effects of dilution considered by Mukherjee and Sen (*loc. cit.*) and by Kruyt and Spek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1919, 25, 1).

(c) The distinction between a normal and an abnormal behaviour on the basis of a difference in the coagulating concentrations is not justified.

* Partial precipitation took place during measurement.